

Marketing Strategies in Improving Purchase Decisions in Businesses Syifa Hydroponic Farming Hydroponics in the City Medan

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Abstract: This research was conducted to analyze marketing strategies in hydroponic farming businesses using price, social media, attitudes and subjective norms as independent variables on purchasing decisions as the dependent variable, and purchase intention as an intervening variable. This research uses TRA theory. This research method is quantitative research with data analysis using Structural Equation Modeling Partial Square (SEM-PLS). This research was conducted at the hydroponic company Syifa Hidroponik in the city of Medan. The sampling technique used the Simple Random Sampling technique and 109 samples were found. The results of this research show that price has a positive influence on purchase intention, social media has a positive influence on purchase intention, attitude has a positive influence on purchase intention, and subjective norms have a positive influence on purchase intention, and purchase intention has a positive influence on purchase decisions.

Keywords: Price, Social Media, Attitude, Subjective Norms, Purchase Intentions, Purchasing Decisions.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Hydroponics is synonymous with cultivating plants without soil. The word "hydroponics" comes from Greek, namely from the words "hydro" which means air, and "ponos" which means work or effort. Literally, hydroponics means "working with air". This term was first used by Dr. William Frederick Gericke in 1937 to describe a method of growing plants without using soil, but using air enriched with nutrients as a plant growth medium (Sutanto, 2015). One The use of hydroponic technology in Indonesia has grown significantly.

History records that hydroponic technology was first introduced in Indonesia in the 1970s, and began to be developed on an industrial scale in 1982. Since then, this technology has become a major highlight in the development of the agricultural sector in Indonesia (Subandi et al., 2020). The development of hydroponic farming in Indonesia, especially for vegetable crops, shows bright prospects. The use of hydroponic technology in Indonesia has opened up new opportunities in the development of the agricultural sector, making a significant contribution to food sustainability and the country's economic growth. This certainly makes hydroponic farming a very profitable business opportunity. Hydroponic plant cultivation has various advantages, one of which is that it uses less water, up to 90% compared to conventional farming and does not

require any land at all, so it can be applied in areas with less fertile soil or even indoors. Plants using hydroponic techniques often grow faster because the nutrients are directly absorbed by the roots. (Lorian, 2023).

Medan City is one of the big cities in Indonesia with high population growth and density, and has great potential for business development, including hydroponic farming. The results from this garden are used for household consumption. Urban commercial farms are established for for-profit business purposes and can be combined with 'commercial kitchens' to produce value-added food products and sell them to farmers markets and restaurants. Hydroponic farming has emerged as an innovative solution to overcome the challenges of urban agricultural land conversion (Garcia, 2022). Syifa Hydroponics is one of the MSMEs that promotes hydroponic cultivation, Syifa Hydroponics. Syifa Hydroponics was founded by Ir. Suardi Raden since 2014 and is located at Jalan Bromo Lorong Amal No.11, Tegal Sari III, Medan Area District, Medan City, North Sumatra. Syifa Hydroponics has hydroponic plant cultivation business products, hydroponic plant consultants, and sells processed products from hydroponic plants. Syifa Hydroponics Medan is an example in the fresh vegetable industry with a focus on hydroponic cultivation in the city of Medan. The hydroponic system has proven to be an effective alternative for farming

in areas with limited land and makes it an attractive option for farmers in Medan (As' ad et al., 2024).

Table 1: Sales of Hydroponic Vegetables at Syifa Hydroponics

Types of vegetables	2020 (Kg)	2021 (Kg)	2022 (Kg)	2023 (Kg)	Price (Kg)/ year
Basil	150 kg	144 kg	100kg	80kg	Rp.80.000
Mustard greens	360 kg	360 kg	240kg	180kg	Rp.20.000
Spinach	200 kg	150 kg	150kg	100 kg	Rp.25.000
Kale	150 kg	120 kg	80kg	80kg	Rp.25.000

Based on the table above, sales of hydroponic vegetables at Syifa Hidroponik will decrease from 2023 to 2020. This decrease has an impact on the sales turnover of hydroponic vegetables which of course also decreases. The decline in vegetable sales at Syifa Hydroponics was caused by several factors, including the fairly high selling price of conventional vegetables. Where for conventionally grown basil vegetables the average price (kg)/year is IDR. 40,000, while mustard greens Rp. 15,000, spinach Rp. 20,000 and kale Rp. 20,000.

Consumers in deciding to buy a product offered are greatly influenced by their perceptions of the price, product, promotion and place (marketing mix) that has been implemented by the company. There is a relationship between price and purchasing decisions. The higher the price, the decision to buy tends to be lower. Conversely, if the price is lower, purchasing decisions tend to increase (Kotler et al., 2005). Social media is a consideration factor in purchasing decisions by providing information and news that attracts consumers' purchasing intentions. Consumers who are interested in information on social media will be influenced in deciding whether to buy or not buy a product (Mileva, 2018). Attitude and subjective norms are formed by an individual's beliefs about the consequences of carrying out a behavior and normative beliefs referenced by people or groups that are considered important to the individual. In other words, a person will consider the results or impact of the behavior as well as the views or expectations of influential people in their life before deciding to act.

The selection of this title is based on the urgency to understand and develop an effective marketing strategy. This analysis is expected to not only help increase sales but also expand the market share of hydroponic products. Thus, this research will make a significant contribution to creating a sustainable and profitable agricultural ecosystem, as well as helping hydroponic businesses overcome the various marketing challenges they face. This is what underlies the development of a hydroponic vegetable business that requires effective marketing strategy analysis to improve purchasing decisions

II. THEORETICAL BASE

A. Marketing Strategy for Hydroponic Products

The marketing mix plays an important role in planning an effective marketing strategy to help a company achieve its goals. The marketing mix is a collection of tactical tools that a company can control and use simultaneously to create the

desired response in the target market. In marketing literature, this combination is known as 4P, which includes Product, Price, Place and Promotion. This 4P concept helps companies design a comprehensive and integrated marketing strategy, which considers various external and internal factors that influence the marketing performance of the product or service (Artana & Sujianto, 2019).

B. Price

Price is one of the most crucial decisions in marketing. In setting prices, companies can use four approaches, namely: market based pricing, cost based pricing, competition based pricing, value based pricing. Market based pricing is setting prices that are adjusted to market expectations. This approach indicates that the product being offered is a commodity and is easily compared with other products and is easily imitated and attacked by products that offer more added value. Cost based pricing means that the company determines production costs first, then sets the price through mark-up. Competition based pricing where the price for a product is determined by the company. Value based pricing means that prices are determined based on the value and benefits attached to the product, not based on costs. The benefits offered are not always at a high price (Vildayanti, 2020).

C. Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is a form of marketing carried out directly or indirectly to increase recognition, awareness, and build memory of a brand, product, or other entity using tools such as microblogging, blogging, content sharing, social bookmarking, and social networking (Riskady & Sulistyowati, 2021). Social media marketing has an influence on purchasing decisions by providing facilities for people to provide online reviews, which can influence consumers' thinking when making purchasing decisions about a product. Purchasing decisions cover various aspects, including what to buy, whether to make a purchase or not, when to buy, where to buy, and how to pay for it (Susan, 2011).

D. Theory of Reasoned Action

The Theory of Reasoned Action explains that there are stages that humans go through in deciding to carry out a behavior. According to Amalia (Amalia, 2018), the first stage is that a person's behavior is determined by their intentions. The Theory of Reasoned Action emphasizes that the most important determinant of a person's behavior is the intention to carry out that behavior. This intention functions as the main indicator that predicts whether someone will carry out an action or not. A person who believes that a particular individual thinks he or she should perform a behavior, and is

motivated to fulfill those expectations. Conversely, if the individual believes that his referent thinks he should not perform the behavior, then he will have a negative subjective norm. A person who believes that a particular individual thinks he or she should perform a behavior, and is motivated to fulfill those expectations. Individuals who are less motivated to follow these references will have relatively neutral subjective norms. The essence of TRA is the assumption that the most important direct determinant of behavior is behavioral intention. The success of this theory in explaining behavior depends on the extent to which a particular behavior is under volitional control, that is, the extent to which the individual can have great control over that behavior (Brownson et al., 2015).

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses quantitative methods. According to (Nadirah et al., 2022), quantitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism. This method uses a specific population and carries out quantitative or statistical data analysis with the aim of testing a predetermined hypothesis. The types and sources of data used in this research are: (1) Primary data is research data sourced directly from respondents and produced by filling in questionnaires that have been given to respondents. (2) Secondary data is research data sourced indirectly from data from visits, historical notes or reports arranged in archives (documentary data). The data analysis method used is structural equation modeling-partial least squares (SEM-PLS). A research hypothesis is a temporary assumption formulated to explain the relationship between variables.

- H1: Price has a significant and positive effect on intention
- H2: Social media has a significant and positive effect on intention
- H3: Attitude has a significant and positive effect on intention
- H4: Subjective norms have a significant and positive effect on intentions
- H5: Intention has a positive effect on purchasing decisions

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Profile of Syifa Hydroponics Medan

Syifa Hydroponics is one of the vegetable processing industries in Medan City, located on Jalan Bromo Lorong Amal No. 11 Terrain. This business started from a husband and wife's hobby of planting makeshift plants next to the house with used goods that were still suitable for use, initially only to supply household vegetables.

As time went by, in 2015 Syifa Hydroponics had the opportunity to take part in an exhibition. From there, this husband and wife couple started their career in the field of hydroponic farming. At the start of her career, Syifa hydroponics only sold fresh vegetables. By planting 2,000 planting points on a 64 square meter building (rooftop) with various vegetables such as mustard greens, kale and spinach. These hydroponic vegetables reach a weight of 85 grams to 100 grams/pot in approximately four weeks, then are sold for Rp. 20,000 to Rp. 25,000 per kilogram. Nowadays, Syifa Hydroponics provides equipment and all kinds of things related to planting with a hydroponic system. Not only that, Syifa hydroponics also innovates by selling several products they grow. This is because not every harvest of Syifa vegetables is sold out. The first derivative product that Syifa Hydroponics sold was vegetable nuggets. Syifa Hydroponics focuses on selling fresh vegetables with a hydroponic system, hydroponic tools and equipment and downstream products from hydroponic vegetables.

➤ Vision – Mission of Syifa Hydroponics Medan

- *Vision:*
More and more people can produce fresh and healthy vegetables, especially in urban areas where land is small, using a hydroponic system.
- *Mission:*
Inviting people to participate in healthier agriculture and think about the environmental impact of not using pesticides with a hydroponic system.

B. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

The characteristics of respondents based on the age of Syifa Hydroponics Medan consumers are as follows:

Fig 1: Pie Chart of Respondent Characteristics based on Age
Source: Data Processed by the Author, 2024

Figure above outlines 26 respondents aged 20-25 years with a percentage of 24%. Respondents aged 26-30 years were 24 people with a percentage of 22%. There were 40 respondents aged 31-35 years with a percentage of 37%. There were 12 respondents aged 36-40 years with a percentage of 11%. And there were 7 respondents aged 26-30 years with a percentage of 6%. It can be concluded that most Syifa Hydroponics Medan consumers are aged 31-35 years.

C. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

Characteristics of respondents based on gender of Syifa Hydroponics Medan consumers are as follows:

Fig 2: Pie Chart of Respondent Characteristics based on Gender
Source: Data Processed by the Author, 2024

Figure above describes 40 respondents with male gender with a percentage of 37%. And respondents with female gender were 69 people with a percentage of 63%. It can be concluded that most consumers of Syifa Hydroponics Medan are women.

D. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education

The characteristics of respondents based on Syifa Hydroponics Medan consumer education are as follows:

Fig 3: Pie Chart of Respondent Characteristics based on Education
Source: Data Processed by the Author, 2024

Figure above outlines 27 respondents with high school/equivalent education, with a percentage of 25%. Respondents with D3 education were 11 people with a percentage of 10%. Respondents with S1 education were 65 people with a percentage of 59%. Respondents with Master's

Degree Education were 4 people with a percentage of 4%. There were 2 respondents with doctoral education with a percentage of 2%. It can be concluded that most Syifa Hydroponics Medan consumers have a Bachelor's degree education.

E. Data Analysis Result

➤ *Validity Test*

Table 2: Validity Test Results Table

	Attitude (X3)	Price (X1)	Buying Decision (Y)	Purchase Intention (Z)	Social Media (X2)	Subjective Norm (X4)
A1	0,853					
A2	0,943					
A3	0,942					
A4	0,979					
A5	0,860					
H1		0,937				
H2		0,939				
H3		0,770				
H4		0,769				
KP1			0,887			
KP2			0,788			
KP3			0,890			
KP4			0,782			
KP5			0,793			
NB1				0,854		
NB2				0,987		
NB3				0,925		
NB4				0,824		
SM1					0,867	
SM2					0,881	
SM3					0,943	
SM4					0,935	
SN1						0,834
SN2						0,867
SN3						0,841
SN4						0,963
SN5						0,937

Source: Data Processed by the Author, 2024

Based on the results of the validity test using SMARTPLS can be seen that the loading factor value on the

statement items for each variable is more than 0.7. This shows that the instrument for each variable is declared valid.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Table 3: Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho a)	Composite reliability (rho c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Price (X1)	0,897	1,003	0,901	0,699
Social Media (X2)	0,764	0,915	0,859	0,643
Attitude (X3)	0,953	0,976	0,963	0,841
Subjective Norm (X4)	0,848	0,914	0,887	0,634
Buying Decision (Y)	0,755	0,813	0,841	0,529
Purchase Intention (Z)	0,825	0,918	0,882	0,669

The variables Price (X1), Social Media (X2), Attitude (X3), Subjective Norm (X4) Purchase Decision (Y), and

Intention (Z) above show very consistent results with a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.70.

➤ *R-Square*

Table 4: Inner Model Test Results (R-Square)

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Buying Decision (Y)	0,635	0,593
Purchase Intention (Z)	0,599	0,565

Based on the results of data processing for R-Square, the R-Square value for Purchase Intentions is 0.599, which indicates that the regression model for the influence of Price, Social Media, Attitude and Subjective Norm on Purchase Intentions has moderate strength because the R-Square value greater 0.50 and less 0.75 ($0.50 < 0.599 < 0.75$). Meanwhile,

the R-Square value for purchasing decisions is 0.635, which shows that the regression model of the influence of price, social media, attitude and subjective norms on purchasing decisions through Purchase Intentions has moderate strength because the R-Square value is smaller than 0.50 and greater than 0.25 ($0.25 < 0.635 < 0.50$).

➤ *Q-Square*

Table 5: Inner Model Test Results (Q-square)

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Purchase Intention (Z)	447,000	384,136	0,141
Buying Decision(Y)	447,000	387,017	0,134
Price (X1)	484,000	484,000	
Social Media (X2)	349,000	349,000	
Attitude (X3)	484,000	484,000	
Subjective Norm (X4)	495,000	495,000	

Based on the results of data processing for Q-Square in Table the Q-Square value is greater than 0. The Q-Square value for purchase intention is 0.134 greater than 0 ($0.134 > 0$) which indicates that the regression model influences price, social media, attitude, and subjective norms on purchase intentions have predictive relevance. Meanwhile, the Q-Square value for purchasing decisions is 0.141 which is greater than 0 ($0.141 > 0$) which indicates that the regression model of the influence of price, social media, attitude and subjective norms on purchasing decisions through purchase intentions has predictive relevance.

F. *Statistical Test*

➤ *Direct Effect*

- Equation 1 ($Z = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon$)

The results of data processing for hypothesis testing in equation 1 are as follows:

Table 5: Hypothesis Test Results for Equation 1

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Price (X1) -> Purchase Intention(Z)	0,052	0,048	0,211	2,246	0,008
Social Media (X2) -> Purchase Intention (Z)	0,036	0,022	0,115	2,317	0,016
Attitude (X3) -> Purchase Intention (Z)	0,148	0,149	0,097	2,517	0,013
Subjective Norm (X4) -> Purchase Intention (Z)	0,272	0,295	0,095	2,851	0,005

Based on the test results the direct influence of price, social media, attitudes and subjective norms on purchase intentions can be explained as follows:

- Effect of Price (X1) on Intention (Z). Based on the test results in table, the regression coefficient value is 0.052 and the t-statistic value is 2.246 with a probability value of 0.008. The probability value is greater than the predetermined error tolerance ($0.008 < 0.05$). This shows that price has a positive and significant effect on intention, so H1 is accepted.

- Influence of Social Media (X2) on Intention (Z). Based on the test results in table, the regression coefficient value is 0.036 and the t-statistic value is 2.317 with a probability value of 0.016. The probability value is smaller than the predetermined error tolerance ($0.016 < 0.05$). This shows that Social Media has a positive and significant effect on Intention, so H2 is accepted.
- Influence of Attitude (X3) on Intention (Z). Based on the test results in table, the regression coefficient value is 0.148 and the t-statistic value is 2.517 with a probability value of 0.013. The probability value is smaller than the predetermined error tolerance ($0.013 < 0.05$). This shows

that Attitude has a positive and significant effect on Intention, so H3 is accepted.

- Influence of Subjective Norms (X4) on Intentions (Z). Based on the test results in table, the regression coefficient value is 0.272 and the t-statistic value is 2.851 with a probability value of 0.005. The probability value is

smaller than the predetermined error tolerance ($0.005 < 0.05$). This shows that Subjective Norm has a positive and significant effect on Intention, so H4 is accepted.

➤ Equation 1 ($Y = \alpha + \beta IZ + \epsilon$)

The results of data processing for hypothesis testing in equation 2 are as follows:

Table 6: Hypothesis Test Results Equation 2

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Purchase Intention (Z) -> Buying decision (Y)	0,067	0,056	0,115	2,583	0,006

Based on the test results in the direct influence of price, social media, attitude and subjective norms on purchasing decisions can be explained as follows:

- Influence of Intention (Z) on purchasing decisions (Y). Based on the test results in table the regression coefficient value is 0.067 and the t-statistic value is 2.583 with a probability value of 0.006. The probability value is smaller than the predetermined error tolerance ($0.006 < 0.05$). This shows that intention has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, so H5 is accepted.

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Price on Purchase Intentions

The research results show that the price variable has a positive and significant influence on purchase intentions for Syifa Hydroponics. Therefore, the better the price perception, the better the purchase intention. If consumers feel that the price of a product is reasonable then this will have a positive effect on consumer motivation to make a purchase, which means that if they want to increase buying interest, then Syifa Hydroponics owners must pay attention to product quality and price. The results of this research are also supported by the characteristics of the respondents who are consumers at Syifa Hidroponik. Respondents who are consumers at Syifa Hydroponics are on average 31-35 years old, at this age most of them are married so price really influences consumers' purchasing intentions. The average characteristic of respondents based on gender is female, and as in general, women really consider price so that it can influence their purchasing intentions. Likewise with the characteristics of respondents based on average education with a bachelor's degree, where respondents or consumers can take more into account the appropriateness of product prices and their consideration of purchasing intentions.

This finding is supported by theory from the opinion expressed by Sandy & Ernungtyas (2020), which revealed that price is one of the conditions that influences consumer purchasing intentions. This is the same as the research results which state that price has a significant influence on purchase intention

B. The Influence of Social Media on Purchase Intentions

The research results show that social media variables have a positive and significant influence on purchase intentions for Syifa Hydroponics. This shows that a consumer's buying interest is influenced by the social media they use. The results of this research are also supported by the characteristics of respondents who are consumers at Syifa Hidroponik. Respondents who are consumers at Syifa Hydroponics are on average 31-35 years old, where at this age most are married and actively use social media so price greatly influences consumers' purchasing intentions. The average characteristic of respondents based on gender is female, and as in general, women really consider reviews or advertisements on social media so that they can influence their purchasing intentions. Likewise with the characteristics of respondents based on average education with a bachelor's degree, where respondents or consumers can take more into account product quality based on promotions on social media and their consideration of purchasing intentions.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Sayekti et al. (2023) and Lestari et al. (2023) shows that social media has a positive and significant influence on online purchase intentions. This shows that social media is one of the factors in increasing consumer purchasing intentions online.

C. The Influence of Attitude on Purchase Intentions

The research results show that the attitude variable has a positive and significant influence on purchase intentions for Syifa Hydroponics. The results of this research are also supported by the characteristics of the respondents who are consumers at Syifa Hidroponik. Respondents who are consumers at Syifa Hydroponics are on average 31-35 years old, at this age most of them are already married so evaluating what they should consume for their families greatly influences consumers' purchasing intentions. The average characteristic of respondents based on gender is female, and as in general, women really consider the positive and negative sides of a product so that it can influence their purchasing intentions. Likewise with the characteristics of respondents based on average education with a bachelor's degree, where respondents or consumers can take more into account the suitability of the product and their consideration of purchasing intentions.

These findings strengthen Ajzen's theory, namely that attitude can be described as an important element in predicting and describing human behavior/actions. Similar research results were found by Mranani & Lastianti (2022) who also showed that attitude had a positive effect on consumer purchase intentions, especially healthy food products. This means that the attitude that consumers have towards food products will increase consumers' purchasing intentions towards these products. This is because attitude reflects consumer awareness of the need to consume healthy food as well as consumer knowledge about food products.

D. The Influence of Subjective Norms on Purchase Intentions

The research results show that the Subjective Norm variable has a positive and significant influence on purchase intentions for Syifa Hydroponics. Previous studies show that subjective norms are a predictor of intention. The positive relationship between subjective norms and purchase intentions can be influenced by external factors such as reference groups and family. Other external factors such as friends, colleagues, and wife, have been found to influence decision making by up to 45% and social and cultural factors, determined by religion, kinship, and social relationships, play an important role in purchase intentions. Consumers are often influenced by friends' input, social factors play an important role and subjective norms influence purchase intentions (Wiyati et al., 2024).

E. Influence of Purchase Intentions on Purchase Decisions

The research results show that the Intention variable has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions at Syifa Hydroponics. This shows that purchasing interest is very determining for consumers to buy or not. According to Mranani & Lastianti (2022), the stage of a respondent's tendency to take an action before actually deciding to make a purchase is called purchase interest. Consumers' buying interest in making purchases can arise as a result of the stimulus offered by the company. Each of these stimuli is designed to influence purchasing actions by consumers.

According to Mranani & Lastianti (2022), the stage of a respondent's tendency to take an action before actually deciding to make a purchase is called purchase interest. Consumers' buying interest in making purchases can arise as a result of the stimulus offered by the company. Each of these stimuli is designed to influence purchasing actions by consumers. According to Swastha and Irawan (2013), purchasing decisions are a problem solving approach to human activities to purchase goods or services to fulfill their desires and needs which consists of recognizing needs and desires, searching for information, evaluating purchasing alternatives, purchasing decisions and behavior. after purchase. Mranani & Lastianti (2022) say that purchasing decisions are a process where consumers evaluate various alternative choices and choose one or more of the necessary alternatives based on certain considerations.

Based on partial research results, it was found that aspects of the attention dimension and interest dimension had a positive and significant relationship with aspects of product type. Respondents before deciding to buy a product at Syifa

Hydroponics first looked for information on what types of products were available at Syifa Hydroponics through friends, family, sellers and social media. Apart from that, respondents were interested in buying amplang at Syifa Hidroponik because of recommendations from friends and family who had already bought products at that place. Based on conditions in the field, respondents decided to buy the product because of the type of amplang product sold at Syifa Hidroponik.

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